

The Special Relativistic $\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ Factor and the Notion of Length in (0,ct)

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We have considered the 2x2 Lorentz transformation of a particle with rest mass m_0 at rest at $x=0$ at t in previous notes. We argued that in the moving frame, one may have an x' and t' , but the constraint $x'/t'=v$ holds which means that $x=0, t=0$ transforms to $x'=0, t'=0$. We suggested that a general 2x2 matrix which achieves this result is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g & gv \\ gv & g \end{vmatrix}$$

In other words, $(x=0, t)$ transforms to (x', t') with $x'=gvt$ and $t'=gt$. In principle, one might consider $g=1$ in this example. In other words, $(0, t)$ is like $x'=vt$ and $t'=t$ in the moving frame like in pre-special relativistic physics. This approach of course breaks the idea of an invariant modulus using x, t , but in pre-special relativistic physics there is no spacetime and one would not really be concerned about such an invariant.

We ask, however, if there is an interpretation for t in $(x=0, t)$. We suggest that one could imagine the distance $L=vt$ and associate it with a time $t=0$. Then $(L, 0)$ would transform to (gL, gvL) . In such a case, $gL/(gLv/c) = 1/v$ and not v as before. The point we make is that if L transforms to L (for $g=1$), then it is strange that time is different, i.e. Lv in the moving frame (if $g=1$). In other words, considering $(0, 0)$ and $(L, 0)$ in the rest frame, one has $(0, 0)$ and $(L, Lv/c)$ for $g=1$ in the moving. In other words, if $(L, 0)$ and $(g, gLv/c)$ represent the same physical point, albeit in different frames, then it seems that g cannot be 1 and that an invariant showing the two states must be the same should involve both x' and t' . This applies both to $(0, t) \rightarrow (gvt, gt)$ and $(L, 0) \rightarrow (gL, gvL)$. Here we set $c=1$. Noting that the same invariant should hold for v and $-v$ suggests a quadratic form and the two transformations suggest a symmetry between x' and t' . This leads to $-t't' + x'x' = \text{invariant}$ and $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. (The minus sign appears if one considers the Lorentz transformation and invariant form also applying to $(0, mocc)$ and (pc, E)).

Special Relativity

One may derive the Lorentz matrix from considerations of a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t as we have done in previous notes. Here we ask: Is there some physical relevance to the value t ? After all, if nothing happens to m_0 , why does one even consider the notion of time? We argue that it is irrelevant whether a clock is ticking in the room. We will return to this point, but first we argue that in a frame moving with $-v$, one should see x' and t' such that $x'/t'=v$. This suggests a matrix of the form:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g & gv \\ gv & g \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1)) \quad \text{to give it some symmetry. Actually one only has } gv=a_{11} \text{ and } g=a_{22}.$$

At this point, g is unknown and a pre-special relativistic approach might be to consider $g=1$ so that $x'=vt$ and $t'=t$. In other words, time has not changed, but the particle has "jumped" from

$x=0$ to $x'=vt$ to be compatible with motion, noting that $x=0, t=0$ transforms to $x'=0, t'=0$ regardless of the value of g .

To consider this issue further, we try to assign a physical sense to t in $(0, t)$. If one is considering a frame moving with $-v$ which watches this particle, then one could suggest the distance: $L=vt$. In other words, t in $(0, t)$ in the rest frame would be equivalent to a distance using the v from the moving frame. One might then consider $(0, 0)$ and $(L=vt, 0)$ in the rest frame.

This transforms to: $(0, 0)$ and $(gL, gLv/c)$ in the moving frame. If $g=1$, then one has the unusual result that L is the same in both frames, but time changes.

If one rejects this, one needs to find a g that is not 1. First one may note that v appears in the transformed results, but both v and $-v$ should yield the same link between frames. This suggests a quadratic form at minimum. Secondly, one has the two transformations: $(0, t) \rightarrow (gvt, gt)$ and $(L, 0) \rightarrow (gL, gLv/c)$. This suggests a quadratic $x'x'$ and a separate quadratic $t't'$. The only question is whether these add or subtract. If one suggests that the transformation must apply to $(0, mocc)$ and (pc, E) , then a minus sign is required. This leads to:

$$g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((2))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that $(x=0, ct)$ for a rest mass point at $x=0, t$ may be interpreted as a length $L=vt$, where $-v$ is the speed of a moving frame. In such a case, one may consider $(x=0, t) \rightarrow (gvt, gt)$ or $(L, t=0) \rightarrow (gL, gvL)$. If one were inclined to think that $g=1$, then $L \rightarrow L$ in the latter case, while time transforms, which would be unlikely. This suggests g is not 1. Considering v and $-v$ yielding the same result leads to the notion of at least a quadratic and the two transformations suggest separate terms for t and x , leading to $-tt + xx$ as an invariant ($c=1$). A minus sign is chosen if one wishes to apply these ideas to $(0, mocc)$ and (pc, E) . One then finds that $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. The point we wish to make in this note is that $(0, t)$ which contains time which does not seem to play any physical role might be linked to a length point $L=vt$, where v is associated with a moving frame speed $-v$.